

Case Study on Sustainability Projects of Sri Lankan Top-notch Apparel Company

M.B.B.U. Mandawala¹, N.P.K. Ekanayake²

¹Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Sri Jayawardhanapura

²Department of Commerce and Financial Management, University of Kelaniya

ABSTRACT: This case study is mainly focused on observing the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) of a top-notch apparel company in Sri Lanka. With this case study authors are expecting to study the willingness and capability of a business to engage in CSR projects and to observe the behaviour of such CSR projects in a selected company. At present, CSR is indeed one of the most debated and discussed topic. Therefore, the purpose of this project is to find out whether the CSR projects undertaken by a company would help to safeguard consumer's preferences and reduced the poverty of the consumer. This study has discouraged authors to recognize that CSR has a positive impact on consumers' behaviour. In many cases, these projects have enabled the company to recruit new employees to the business, thus reduced employee recruitment cost. The selected group's principal CSR efforts are driven by the central corporate theme of water and are planned and executed by the "Bindu" Foundation established by the Group for the purpose. These efforts represent a long-term commitment to increasing the availability of water and the provision of safe drinking water to those most in need. Mainly, their CSR projects are based on categories such as; Education, Health, Community Live-hood Development, Environment, Arts and Culture. The company embrace following CSR projects under these categories. Ran Daru Thilina, Model Village, Blood Drive, P.A.C.E program, Care for Their Own project, and Rasadiya Mangallaya. Through these projects, this apparel leader aims to alleviate the poverty of the society, uplift the lifestyles of the employees and consumers, minimize the harm caused by the business, protect the environment and enhance their business reputation.

KEYWORDS: Top-notch Apparel Company, Corporate Social Responsibility, Stakeholders, Sustainability Development

1. INTRODUCTION

The selected top-notch apparel company plays a critical part in the Sri Lankan economy as the country's largest contributor to GDP. It employs the most people in Sri Lanka's export sector and generates the most foreign exchange. Company's Group is a prominent apparel manufacturer in the South Asia, with a goal of being the best in the world "The Inspired Solution for Branded Clothing". Their roots are firmly planted in Sri Lanka. Since then, they have rapidly grown their reach both within the country and abroad, employing over 41,000 people in 28 factories in Sri Lanka, five in India, and one in Bangladesh.

The company was formed in Sri Lanka in 1969 with the help of Martin Trust, an American who is widely considered as the creator of Sri Lanka's modern garment business. The company originated as a conglomerate that was legally a part of the Omar Group in 1972. The firm launched a branch in Seeduwa in 2008, and the Seeduwa branch was awarded the world's first LEED Platinum accreditation (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design). The Ceylon Chamber of Commerce named the company one of the top-ten best corporate companies in the country in 2009. In 2011, this company also became the world's first apparel company to obtain the ISO 50001 standard system certification scheme.

1.1. GOVERNANCE

Strong governance also ensures that their business activities comply with local laws and regulations, and that the Group operates in accordance with professional and ethical standards in order to achieve long-term, sustainable, and healthy growth. Their governance framework integrates the processes and structures put in place by the Board to inform, direct, manage, and monitor the organization's activities in order to achieve its goals. The "Three Lines of Defense Model" is used by the company to structure Governance risk and control responsibilities across the business, with the Board of Directors serving as the ultimate

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authority providing oversight for each of the three lines of defense. A strong, effective, and qualified Board of Directors is at the heart of the Group's Governance structure, committed to maintaining rigorous Corporate Governance, sound internal controls, and a structured Risk Management framework in order to earn the trust of their employees, customers, and the community.

2. SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY OF THE COMPANY

In this company, Sustainability is far from being an unfamiliar concept, becoming more a way of life as they continue their commitment to actively pursue and invest in innovative technologies and processes that help minimize the overall environmental impact of their operations". Over the years, the company's journey toward sustainability has set the stage for other manufacturing organizations as they continue to introduce and reinforce sustainable practices that have helped reduce their manufacturing operations' carbon footprint. In 2008, this company's Green factory in Seeduwa became the world's first apparel manufacturing facility to be rated Platinum under the US Green Building Council's LEED Green Building Rating System. This is also the world's second highest rating for an apparel manufacturing plant. In addition, with the goal of achieving carbon neutrality across their operations by 2020, they embarked on a broad 10-year strategy that is anchored to actionable Group-wide targets and recognizes the unique biodiversity of each nation in which they operate with a commitment to manage environmental performance without interruptions as part of this continuous journey, they launched their Eco Index.

2.1. CSR and Stakeholders

Individuals, groups, and organizations that have been identified as being significantly impacted by their operations are listed below. The perspectives of stakeholders provide them with advice and encouragement, as they'll as challenge their thinking, giving them greater clarity on the impacts of their business activities on a small and large scale. They regularly engage with their stakeholders through their various communication platforms to gain a better understanding of priority issues and to refine their shared vision for long-term growth. Their Stakeholder Engagement mechanism is an evolving process that, above all, aims to prioritize sustainability.

2.2. Group Sustainability Model Of The Company

This report describes the sustainability strategies they created in accordance with the Group's four-pillar sustainability model. They are people, the planet, the community, and the supplier.

2.2.1. People

In fact, the company readily admits that their team of over 41,000 employees spread across Sri Lanka, India, and Bangladesh is the true architect of their success. They believe that each employee brings his or her own set of skills and ideas to work every day to help the company achieve the goals outlined in their mission statement. At this company, this is referred to as the RITE way, in which each individual believes in, works toward, and ensures that their every action represents their core values of Respect, Inspiration, Togetherness, and Ethics. These values are instilled in day-to-day work life, providing them with the impetus to make RITE choices, RITE decisions, and foster the RITE attitude that will propel this brand forward.

2.2.1.1. Occupational Health and Safety

The company takes pride in its safety culture, which has led to investments in establishing and maintaining an in-house medical facility staffed by qualified doctors and staff at each of its 34 factories. The company takes pride in its safety culture, which has led to investments in each of its 34 factories in establishing and maintaining an in-house medical facility staffed by qualified doctors and staff associated with their business activities. All factories' safety protocols are regularly monitored, and their safety systems are subjected to stringent safety system inspections twice a year.

SAFETY ASSESSMENT SERIES STANDARD OHSAS 18001

Every factory in this firm has a Health and Safety committee that represents the entire workforce. The committee is made up of a cross-functional team that is chaired by the Plant Operations Manager at each location. The Plant Safety Officer, who is also a committee member, is responsible for tracking all accidents and incidents, conducting safety reviews, and reporting on performance against internal targets. The Safety Committee is held fully accountable for workforce safety at each factory, and as such, it is required to meet at least once a month to review the current safety record, with reported breaches being escalated for further action via the Incident Escalation Process.

2.2.1.2. Training and Development

They are committed to ensuring that all of their employees have access to learning, development, and training opportunities in order to gain the knowledge and skills required to perform their assigned role within the Group. Employees, according to this company, can sharpen their competencies through training and development in order to support the Group's strategic objectives and future growth trajectory. The effectiveness of a training program is assessed using post-training feedback forms,

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which are used to document new skills learned, their relevance to a specific job role, and their effectiveness in day-to-day application.

2.2.1.3. P.A.C.E Program

The Executive leadership training agenda is made up of a range of robust training modules that allow different Executive-level employees to upgrade their competency and acquire functional and leadership skills. The Executive leadership training agenda is made up of a range of robust training modules that allow different Executive-level employees to upgrade their competency and acquire functional and leadership skills. P.A.C.E PROGRAM A group of 181 company's Associates recently completed Gap Inc.'s Personal Advancement and Career Enhancement Program for female workers in the apparel industries. The program provides workers with foundational skills, technical training and support to help them advance in the workplace and in their personal lives. Gap Inc.'s P.A.C.E. program is designed to inspire and help female employees gain the skills and confidence they need to advance at work and in life. P.A.C.E. Graduates have progressed they'll in their careers and contributed more to their workplaces, their peers and their families. Launched in 2007, Gap Inc. Operates the P.A.C.E. program in 16 countries including India, Cambodia, Vietnam, Bangladesh, China, Indonesia, Pakistan, Jordan, Myanmar and Sri Lanka, and has trained more than 65,000 women. Graduates are more productive, have lower rates of absenteeism and are promoted faster than factory workers who do not participate in the program. In addition to the P.A.C.E. program, the company has also graduated 35 female mechanics that completed on-going in-house training courses on sewing machine maintenance and repair in yet another example of the group's commitment to the empowerment of female employees.

2.2.1.4. Female Mechanics Training Program

Highlighting this commitment, the company took another significant step in its ongoing efforts to promote gender equality across the Group through targeted initiatives to train female Mechanics through a special in-house training course on sewing machine maintenance and repair. Penetrating what was once a male dominated field, the 19 female Associates from four business clusters of the the company Group completed the intensive four-month training programme that covered 10 types of sewing machines and encompassed a comprehensive range of technical skills. The 19 female Mechanics that completed the course they're examined via a practical test, a written test, and by their manuals and record keeping.

2.2.1.5. "RASADIYA MANGALYA" Annual Award

Annual Awards 2017 'Rasadiya Mangalya' for the seventh year running, the company's 'Rasadiya Mangalya' annual event, which honored the 27 employees from Sri Lanka, 10 from overseas locations for their contribution to the progress of their Group in 2016, was held for the seventh consecutive year. Every EOY and SOY received both a prize award and a study tour sponsored by the company for those attached to overseas facilities in China, India or Bangladesh. The event also included mechanical excellence awards with Rs.2 million in cash awards given to three individual Mechanics and their respective teams that secured the first three places in the annual 'Mech Challenge' – a Group-wide competition in mechanical proficiency.

2.2.1.6. "RASADIYA THARU" Talent Competition

The 2017 event consisted of three separate competitions - 'Rasadiya Gee Tharuwa' , where four finalists they are selected from 250 participants who competed in the preliminary rounds of the competition; 'Rasadiya Narthana Tharu' , where six troupes of dancers they are shortlisted from 18 teams that participated in the preliminary rounds of the contest and 'Rasadiya Nivedana Tharu' , a new competition introduced in 2017 where three finalists they are selected from 60 that vied for the prize, performing on stage before panels of celebrity judges. At the end of an evening of high-quality entertainment viewed by 5,000 The company Associates, the coveted title of The company 'Rasadiya Gee Tharuwa' for 2017 was won by Sanjeewa Pushpakumara of The company Casualwear, Ratmalana, while the the company 'Rasadiya Narthana Tharu' title was won by the dance troupe of The company Fast Fashion, Avissawella, and the the company 'Rasadiya Nivedana Tharu', was won by H.G. Conducted for the Non-Executive employees, Rasadiya Kusalanya tournament is considered a significant contributor to the popularization of volleyball and the development of players from rural areas, while promoting employee interaction and team spirit within the Group.

2.3. Planet

The strategy embodies their commitment to manage their environmental performance so as not to disrupt the unique biodiversity of the countries in which they operate. To gauge their progress, the company has implemented the Eco Index, a tool that helps evaluate environmental performance across their factories and SBUs and makes necessary improvements to processes on an ongoing basis. Research & Development and Training are the other key pillars that support environmental management strategy the company's investments in research and development are twofold; to generate environmentally sound products and to identify new manufacturing technologies that lessen the environmental impact of their activities. They are also currently in the process of conducting an Environmental Aspect Impact Assessment to identify all the environmental impacts at every step of their manufacturing process.

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2.3.1. Energy

Underpinning their efforts in this regard is Eco Eye; the Group's energy and environment system through which they expect to meet target of carbon neutral operations by 2020. Solar plants installed at three of their facilities: The company Essentials Koggala, India Apparel City and The company Essentials Batticaloa, currently generate sufficient solar power to meet 10% of the Group's annual energy requirement. Capable of meeting 100% of the factory's energy requirement, the installation represents a feather in their cap, as it is the largest solar PV installation in the country.

2.3.2. Eco-Caliper

Eco-Caliper is a Sustainability team energy monitoring package used to collect energy use data from fabrics, sales agencies and the rest of the Group. The Eco-Caliper is a dynamic tool used to monitor utility and usage patterns, which connect all Building Management Systems (BMS) to Mini Energetic Monitoring Systems installed at the company factories throughout the group. Under Eco-Caliper, baselines are defined for all factories based on historic data, while data on energy consumption and machinery type and model used by each factory are collected and analyzed, ensuring that factories are always benchmarked with a similar operation.

2.3.3. Energy Consumption Within the Organization

Reduction of energy consumption			
Renewable Sources	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17
Per USD Energy (KJ/USD)	1,680.64	1,448	1,414
Reduction (Absolute)- (KJ/USD)		232,953	34,079
Reduction (Percentage)		13.9%	2.4 %

2.3.4. Emission

Which is why at the company, they are dedicated to reducing emissions from their operations, for they believe that in this way they can contribute towards the global campaign to mitigate the risks of climate change and global warming. Having tracked their emissions for two consecutive years, they have understood that as their business expands, it is imperative that they operate more efficiently in order to reduce GHG emissions per unit of production. They are also continuously researching new innovative techniques, which they can use to improve their processes and streamline energy usage in the production floor.

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- The base year was chosen as 2014 / 2015, as their, previous Sustainability Report was published then.
- The Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol was followed in doing these calculations.
- The grid emission factors they are taken from the Sustainable Energy Authority, Sri Lanka.
- The chosen consolidation approach is equity share
- Scope 3 emissions cover the transportation of their Associates

- The chosen ratio denominator is the organization's revenue in USD.
- Scope 1, Scope 2 and Scope 3 have been included for the above calculations.
- The ratio uses energy consumed within the organization.
- All gases have been included in the above calculations.

Reduction of GHG emissions			
Year	Reduction (tones of CO ₂ (e))	Reduction (tones of CO ₂ (e)/USD)	Percentage
2015/16	2804	14.14	2.63
2016/17	8248	4.95	7.95

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2.4. Water

Having understood that reducing water consumption within their manufacturing processes is a considerable challenge given their growing business, in the interest of taking more affirmative action, they have further categorized their water footprint as follows: Blue Water the volume of surface and ground water consumed during their production processes Green Water The volume of rainwater consumed in the production process Grey Water The volume of fresh water required to assimilate the load of pollutants based on natural background concentrations and existing ambient water quality standards Waste water recycling is also an important part of their water management strategy. In the recent past, they have made considerable investments to implement processes that allow us to reclaim and reuse water. In doing so, they anchorages their employees to put forth ideas and innovations for water saving techniques that are likely to have a positive impact on the Group's long-term water footprint.

WATER GOALS

- ✓ Clean drinking water for all employees
- ✓ ZERO Water Wastage
- ✓ ZERO Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals
- ✓ Maintaining occupant water consumption standard at 10L/clocked hour-across Apparel manufacturing plants

2.5. Waste

That is why they try to reduce the amount of waste they produce and thus reduce the amount of waste that they send to sites on a daily basis. With this as a priority, they hope that the whole Group of company will achieve zero waste landfill status by 2020. They ensure that 100% of the company waste is disposed of in such a way that their management and compliance staff is central to ensuring that national laws and regulations concerning water generation and waste management are strictly complied with.

2.6. Suppliers

Suppliers are an important component of the value chain because the supply chain's dependability and continuity underpin the ability to consistently deliver on brand promise. A large number of contractors, traders, resellers, and service providers are also part of the company supply chain, all of whom contribute to the company promise of Inspired Solutions. Their supply chain has been developed to allow them to provide their customers with personalized service and exceptional products.

2.6.1. Supplier Evaluation

You select providers and partners on the basis of your ability to supply the product or service you request while respecting your legal and ethical standards. Its supply chain function is governed by the "Five Basic Vendor Rights," namely right quality, right source, right timetable, right amount and right price, which assess and select suitable suppliers and service providers, and in the approval of appropriate contract parties.

2.6.2. Supplier Development

They are invested in working with their suppliers to understand how ongoing changes in their businesses may impact their operations, as they will as the society and environment. They mentor their suppliers and encourage them to improve their

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effectiveness and keep pace with the evolving needs of the The company Group. They also offer support through specific training programmers that encourage them to improve their social and environmental performance.

2.7. Community

Led by the Group's RITE (Respect, Inspiration, Togetherness and Ethics) principles, they strive to contribute to the vitality and they'll being of communities surrounding their work sites through the provision of stable job opportunities, improved sanitation facilities, and overall higher living standards. They are keen to make a clear and positive contribution to the community through systematic interventions that will enhance the they'll being of underserved communities in areas where the Group has a presence. In this context, they aim to address acute social needs that are considered national priorities in the countries in which operate.

2.7.1. CARE OF THEIR OWN

locations	Beneficiaries	
	2015 / 16	2016 /17
BAT Katunayake	4	5
BAT Polonnaruwa	46	39
BCI Ekala	1	7
BCW Girithale	20	5
BCW Rathmalana	9	8
BCW Rideegama	31	12
BCW Seeduwa	8	5
BEL Batticaloa	31	24
BEL Hambantota	18	-
BEL Kahawatte	23	27

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BEL Koggala	13	12
BEL Nivithigala	24	15
BEL Rambukkana	37	38
BEL	2	1

"Care for Their Own", the flagship project of the company is an ongoing initiative to meet the immediate water needs of their employees. The project was first initiated in 2006 after they discovered that many of their employees and their communities are facing grave issues in their quest to access clean water for their daily needs. Their employees are requested to provide the Foundation information regarding the needs of their communities along with supporting data.

2.7.2. Model Village

The aim of the project is to empathy communities in areas where the Group has a manufacturing presence. The first phase of the project aims to resolve water-related issues faced by people residing within a five-kilometer radius of the Group's factories. The second phase of the project seeks to make a broader social impact by addressing water supply and sanitation conditions of communities located within a ten-kilometer radius of the specific company factory site.

2.7.3. Hebetate For Humanity

The Group has cooperated with the Habitat for Humanity Sri Lanka Foundation to provide financial help to rebuilt homes for employees of the Group whose homes were entirely destroyed after the floods and landslides in May 2016 in response to a demand for help in the face of extreme conditions leading to severe flooding and slipping in 12 districts. Another 47 employees house whose homes they have been partly damaged received assistance to repair them.

2.7.4. Ran Daru Thilina

The company 'Ran Daru Thilina' initiative includes the children of 4,971 The company Associates who work in 22 Sri Lankan apparel manufacturing locations. Since its inception in 2016, the program has proven to be a sterile of relief for children ranging in age from nursery to Grade 5, with each child receiving a pack containing items needed for his or her academic year. Furthermore, the 'Ran Daru Scholarships' scheme provides financial assistance to children of Associates who excelled in the Grade 5 scholarship examination.

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2.7.5. Blood Drive

Having understood that a sustained and consistent supply of blood to the National Blood Transfusion Service is a national priority, employees of the Group donated 4,090 units of blood in 2016-17, a move that reaffirms the Group's status as the largest corporate blood donor in Sri Lanka for the seventh successive year. In appreciation of the Group's enduring commitment to the cause of blood donation, the NBTS recently presented the company with a special plaque for being the largest corporate blood donor in the country during the last 12 months. The highest annual volume donated by the Group to the NBTS to date, was blood collected at 27 manufacturing locations in Sri Lanka over a period of several months.

2.7.6. Kalani River Multi-Stakeholder Partnership (KRMP)

The KRMP is a sustainable development initiative to balance the development of livelihoods, community and industry, as they will ensure the safety of drinking water services for the communities who live along the Kelani River. The Kelani River basin is home to 25% of Sri Lanka's population and provides drinking water for a rapidly expanding population of over 3 million, for the Colombo and Greater Colombo areas. Due to the complexity and multi-sector nature of the issues involved in the Kelani River Basin, the International Union for Conservation of Nature, in early 2016, initiated the KRMP project as a private-public-community partnership to ensure the river basin's sustainable development for present and future generations, with funding from UNICEF, under the guidance of the Central Environment Authority and with the participation of over 50 agencies.

3. WORLD FIRST PLATINUM AWARD GREEN FACTORY – THE ECO CENTRE- SEEDUWA

The company converted their 30-year-old 130,000 sq ft factory complex in Seeduwa consisting of three sewing plants into a green factory at a cost of US \$ 3 million whereby receiving Platinum Award under the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design Green Building Rating System of the US Green Building Council the first apparel factory in the world to receive this highest award with the highest grading, yet unmatched anywhere else to date. It also received the highest honor of being judged as the National Winner for Sri Lanka at the Energy Globe Awards 2008 in the Air Category held at Prague by the Energy Globe Foundation. The company through this refurbishment achieved a reduction of carbon emissions by 80% and water consumption by 58% and an energy saving of 80%, and zero solid waste to landfills eco-friendly indicators as yet unmatched by any re-designed Green Plant anywhere in the world. State of the art equipment and material used in this project include a screw-type chiller unit which provides energy-efficient air-conditioning for the entire factory and special prismatic material which allows only the solar light to penetrate barring the accompanying heat and sophisticated new light emitting diodes as task lights to provide light at needle point supplementing the natural light provided by the skylights (Bay lights are used only on cloudy or rainy days).

4. THE ABOVE FIGURE SHOWS THE CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY CONTINUUM. NOW LET'S SEE HOW THE COMPANY'S CSR PROJECTS AND STRATEGIES INTERACT WITH THAT THEORY.

1. Maximum firms' profit to the exclusion of all else.

All companies must maximize their profits to participate in CSR activities. Profit maximization is having a direct impact on the activities of CSR. Their decision was based on their annual profit, how much money they spend on CSR activities each year. In this respect, the company has made a very high annual profit from its companies. Their annual profits reflect about US\$1,465,000 in their report.

2. Do what it takes to make a profit, skirt the law, and fly below social radar

Moreover, the company must adhere to the rules and regulations of the country while maximizing profit and profit must be ethical. In conformity with Sri Lankan law, the company operates legally. Particularly through adherence to their employees' laws, they run their businesses as employees' regulations. They are concerned especially about safety and occupational health. It is very important that an environment is created in which staff can work easily.

For example - Eco Centre- Seeduwa, the world first platinum award green factory.

3. Fight social responsibility initiatives

The company takes great care of its company's social responsibilities. They focus primarily on their employees living around their factories' drinking water and sanitation.

Examples- care of their own project, Model village project

4. Comply, what is legally required

After considered social responsibility, they have to consider minimum legal requirements

Examples – GRI content index

ISO and SLS standards

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5. Do more than required

In addition to the legal requirements the company has concern about the philanthropic. It is the thing more than the legal requirements.

Examples- Ran daru thilina programe, Ran Daru Scholarship, Blood donation projects – Blood Drives

6. Articulate social value objectives

The company also focus on the irradiate poverty and the clean water and sanitation facilities of the community.

7. Integrate social objectives and business goals

Organizations have to form their business goals such as profit maximization in ordered to do a social service.

8. Lead the industry and the other businesses with best practices

A business should follow their CSR activities and other activities as a role model for society and other businesses.

7. ANALYSIS OF IMPROVEMENT ON CSR ACTIVITIES BY THE ORGANIZATION IN PAST THREE YEARS

7.1. RANDARU THILINA / RANDARU SCHOLARSHIP PROGRAMME

Year	Number of Beneficiaries	Area	Nature of Project
2016 Randaru Thilina	4971		Donate school stationaries
2017 Randaru Thilina	5700	Batticola, Girithale, Polonnaruwa, Nivithigala, Koggala, Rambukkana, Kahawatta, Pannala	Donate school stationaries and other school equipment from nursery to grade 5
2017 Randaru Scholarship	4969 children of employees		Give Scholarships for Grade 5 Students

4.1. Model Village

4.2. Care Of Their Own Project

“Care of Their Own,” the company's flagship project, is an ongoing effort to meet the immediate water needs of their employees. They have increased their investment in the project over the years by constructing infrastructure that touches the lives of more people each year.

The following chart shows the shortcomings of beneficiaries of the project in 2015/16 and 2016/17.

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4.3. Reduction of the Emission

Reduction of GHI emission in the year of 2015/16 and 2016/17 has gradually increased over the years. The following chart shows the details of the emission reduction of the company.

Year	Reduction (Tones CO ₂ (e))	of	Reduction (tones CO ₂ (e)/USD)	of	Percentage
2015/16	2804		14.14		2.63%
2016/17	8248		4.95		7.95%

4.4. Reduction of Energy Consumption

Reduction of energy consumption

Renewable Sources	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17
Per USD Energy (KJ/USD)	1,680.64	1,448	1,414
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4.5. Greenhouse Gases Emission Intensity

Greenhouse gases emission intensity has gradually increased over the year of 2015 2016 and 2017. These figures are as follows for the years 2014/15, 152.68 2015/16 , 138.58 and 2016/17 133.63

5. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENTS ON CSR

- They can also support to O/L and A/L students for their education for a better future through their "Randaru Thilina" programme, therefore they can sustain for a long-term
- They can also provide some facilities to orphanage children, old age homes and disabled people, therefore it will improve their good will among people
- They can improve positive policies on labors more and more such like, introduce new compensation schemes, improve their workplace safety, provide allowances, bonuses, entertainment activities and etc.
- They can also introduce some types of insurance policies on employees.
- They can reduce pollutions while providing a renewable, economical alternative to electricity.
- Can offer employees to paid parental leave, which can be taken at any time whether it is the first year of child's life or another time that suits their needs.
- They can provide charitable causes each year from non-profits through philanthropy such as food banks.
- They should follow ethical behaviour such as participating in Fair-trades and socially and environmentally conscious investments.
- They can provide sponsorships for sport clubs, welfare associations, unions, preschool programmes, play grounds, children parks and etc.
- They can promote healthy eating habits and healthy life styles amongst employees.

If they will also follow above practices on CSR activities, they can improve further more on CSR and can be sustain a long term of a period.

6. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this report is to examine the CSR activities of a top-notch apparel company in Sri Lanka. They conduct CSR activities in accordance with their four-pillar sustainability framework, which includes people, planet, supplier, and community. They fulfill their corporate social responsibilities by addressing the four pillar elements. They have been one of the leading companies by adhering to their RITE principles (Respect, Inspiration, Togetherness and Ethics). When they consider new projects that are most beneficial to people, they can ensure their long-term sustainability.

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